

Floatable Ion Associates Formed in the System Iridium(III)-Tin(II)-Chloride-Basic Dye

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Sparingly soluble (in aqueous solutions) ion associates of polyvalent anionic iridium complexes, formed in hydrochloric acid medium containing tin(II) with basic dyes (rhodamine 6G, malachite green or crystal violet) collect on the phase boundary or on the walls of the separatory funnel, when shaken with solvents of low polarity. The separated floatation compounds dissolve in polar solvents. Optimum conditions for complete floatation of iridium compounds are found. Molar ratios (Ir : Sn : dye) in these compounds are determined spectrophotometrically and suitable formulae are proposed.

A NIONIC complexes of many elements with appropriate ligands, formed with basic dye ion associates (ion pairs), and having a molar ratio anion : basic dye = 1 : 1, are extracted by nonpolar solvents. This has been utilized for a long time in extraction-spectrophotometric methods for determination of elements^{1,2}. Some ion associates with basic dyes are not extracted when the aqueous phase is shaken with solvents of low polarity, but collect at the phase boundary or on the walls of the separatory funnel. In this case the anions are polyvalent and the number of monovalent cations of the dye in ion associates is more than one (2 to 5). This process is some kind of floatation of sparinglysoluble ion associate without participation of a surface active substance, usually added in typical floatation process. Precipitates separated from aqueous and organic solvent phases and washed, are soluble in some polar solvents. The solutions obtained can form a basis of very sensitive, so called, floatation-spectrophotometric methods³.

It is known that most of the platinum metals form polyvalent anionic complexes in hydrochloric acid medium in presence of tin(II)⁴⁻⁶, forming mixed complexes with Cl⁻ and SnCl₂⁻ ligands. This work is devoted to a study of ion associates given by such complex of iridium with some basic dyes.

Experimental

Apparatus and Reagents :

A Specord UV-VIS recording and a VSU-2P spectrophotometer with 1 cm cells were used for absorbance measurements. Standard iridium solution (1 mg/ml) was prepared by dissolving 0.5970 g of iridium(III) chloride (Koch-Light) in 2 M HCl with the addition of 5 ml of 5% NaCl solution. The solution was standardized gravimetrically with thionalide⁷. Working solutions were prepared by diluting with 2 M HCl.

Radioisotope ¹⁹²Ir, ammonium hexachloroiridate(IV) in 0.1 M HCl was employed. The dyes were purified by precipitation from ethanolic solutions by addition of a 5-fold excess of diethyl ether. The

strength of the dye solutions was rhodamine 6G (R6G) 2×10^{-3} M (approx. 0.1%), malachite green (MG) and crystal violet (CV) 1×10^{-3} M (about 3.6 $\times 10^{-3}$ % and 4.0 $\times 10^{-3}$ %, respectively). Stannous chloride was used as 10% solution of SnCl₂·2H₂O in 2 M HCl.

Procedure :

An acid (HCl) solution containing 10 μ g of iridium is evaporated to dryness on a boiling water bath. Suitable volumes of SnCl₂ solution and HCl are added to obtain the appropriate acidity. The solution is heated on a boiling water bath for 10-15 min, allowed to cool to room temperature, transferred to a separatory funnel, the dye solution is added, volume made upto 20 ml and the acidity is adjusted. 5 ml of floating organic solvent is then added and shaken for 1 min. The water and organic phases are separated carefully and precipitate is washed and dissolved in the polar solvent. The absorbance of the solutions is measured at 530 nm in the case of the system with R6G, at 627 nm with MG, and at 595 nm with CV, against reagent blanks prepared in the same way.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary studies :

Preliminary experiments were carried out to find the basic dyes, which would form floatable ion associates with anionic iridium complex formed in SnCl₂-HCl medium. The tests involved xanthene, triphenylmethane and azine dyes, commonly used in analytical chemistry^{1,2}. The acidity in these experiments was fixed from 0.5 to 6 M HCl. A 30-60 fold molar excess of the basic dye with respect to iridium (10 μ g) was used. The aqueous solutions were shaken with di-isopropyl ether, benzene, toluene and chloroform.

Only ion associates of the anionic iridium complex with rhodamine 6G, malachite green and crystal violet are floated. The sparingly soluble compounds collect on the phase boundary or on the walls of the separatory funnel.

Conditions of the floatation :

The floating solvents appeared the best are di-isopropyl ether for the ion associates of iridium with rhodamine 6G and malachite green and benzene for ion associate with crystal violet. In these systems, the sparingly soluble compounds accumulate on the walls of the separatory funnel.

The phase volume ratio has no effect on complete separation of the iridium as ion associate. The iridium in separated compounds and in solutions was determined radiometrically. A relatively long shaking of phases in separatory funnel (about 1 min) is necessary. The best concentration of HCl in the aqueous phase during the floatation is 0.4-0.6 M, 2.0-2.4 M and 2.3-2.7 M for malachite green, crystal violet and rhodamine 6G, respectively.

For the complete separation of iridium during a floatation process in the form of a sparingly soluble ion associate, a 55-fold molar excess of rhodamine 6G (with respect to iridium) is necessary. In the cases of malachite green and crystal violet, these molar excesses are 60 and 12, respectively. These dependences are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Dependence of the formation of iridium ion associate on the molar excess of basic dye: 1—rhodamine 6G, 2—malachite green, 3—crystal violet. Absorbances of the solutions measured against the blanks.

The ion pair of the SnCl_2 ion with rhodamine 6G separates together with the anionic iridium complex-basic dye associate. It is decomposed when the precipitate is washed with 2.5 M HCl. The excess of the dye can be removed nearly completely by shaking the precipitate and the di-isopropyl ether with 3 portions of 2.5 M HCl. The floated ion associates of iridium with malachite green and crystal violet are less stable than the ion associate with rhodamine 6G. Washing the precipitates with solutions of similar acidity as that used during floatation leads to decomposition of the floated compounds. The isolated precipitates of iridium with MG and CV can be washed only by shaking with the floating solvents (di-isopropyl ether and benzene, respectively).

Dissolution of the separated and washed ion associates in acetone, methanol, ethanol and

dimethylformamide (DMF) was examined. In the case of the system with rhodamine 6G the precipitate dissolves in the latter three solvents after a little shaking. The dissolution in acetone is immediate. The absorption spectra of the ion associate in these solvents differ insignificantly from the spectrum of the dye in water, with respect to the position of λ_{max} . The absorbance of the acetone solution does not change for a long time.

The ion associate with malachite green dissolves in DMF very slowly and in acetone after a little shaking. Dissolution in methanol and ethanol is immediate. The colour of these solutions does not change for several hours in darkness.

The ion associate with crystal violet dissolves readily in all solvents examined. It should be mentioned that in some preparations of DMF (presumably containing admixtures of reducing agents), the colour intensity of the dye decreases. The solutions of the crystal violet associate in various solvents exhibit small differences in the position of λ_{max} . The stability of the absorbance of solutions depends on the intensity and nature of the incident light.

Composition of the floated compounds :

The molar ratios of iridium to dye in the isolated and washed compounds were determined with the aid of the logarithmic method of Bent and French⁶ (Fig. 2). The data obtained indicate the molar ratio of iridium to crystal violet as 1 : 1, to malachite green as 1 : 3, and to rhodamine 6G as 1 : 4. These results were confirmed by absorbance

Fig. 2. Determination of the molar ratios Ir : basic dye in the floated compounds by the Bent and French method: 1—crystal violet, 2—rhodamine 6G, 3—malachite green.

measurements of the ion associate solutions containing known amounts of iridium, and of solutions of the dye salts (taken in suitable amounts) in solvents used.

In order to determine the number of tin atoms per one iridium atom in the washed compounds, they were mineralized and the tin in solutions

obtained was determined spectrophotometrically with phenylfluorone⁹. The ratios Ir : Sn calculated on the basis of the average result of several tin determinations were 1 : 5.2, 1 : 4.2, and 1 : 4.3 in the compounds of rhodamine 6G, malachite green and crystal violet, respectively. The postulated ratios of metals in the compounds are 1 : 5 or 1 : 4. The higher experimental results are undoubtedly due to contamination of the precipitates with tin not bound in the iridium compounds.

Bearing in mind that the oxidation state of iridium in presence of tin(II) is 3 and the coordination number of iridium is 6, the formulae of the floated compounds can be proposed.

The compound with rhodamine 6G can be postulated to be $[(R6G^+)_5IrCl_2(SnCl_2)_2]^{2-} \cdot [(R6G^+)(SnCl_2)]$. It follows from this formula that the compound is not a simple ion associate but an adduct of the iridium ion associate and of the $SnCl_2$ anion associate with dye. This adduct can be considered stable because it does not decompose during washing the precipitate.

The formula, $[MG^+]_3[IrCl_2(SnCl_2)_2]^{2-}$ can be proposed for the malachite green compound. In the floated compound with crystal violet the ratio of components Ir : Sn : CV is 1 : 4 : 1. In this case it is difficult to suggest a probable formula.

When the floatation of the ion associates with malachite green and crystal violet (triphenylmethane dyes) is carried out in light, the results show poor reproducibility. The lower results (absorbances of ion associates in polar solvents) are due to

diminishing colour intensity of the pseudo solution prepared for floatation. The colour intensity decreases faster with higher concentration of tin(II). This effect is due to the photochemical reduction of malachite green and crystal violet to their inactive leuco forms. Light accelerates the reduction owing to polarization of electron structures of the dyes¹⁰.

Flotation of the ion associates in the systems iridium(III)-tin(II)-chloride-R6G (MG or CV) can form a basis for sensitive floatation-spectrophotometric determination of iridium.

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